

Conductance of Potassium Chloride in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 40°

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Measurements of conductance of potassium chloride in 10, 20 and 30% dioxane — water mixtures (wt. % of dioxane) at 40° have been made as per the procedure given earlier¹. The methods of Fuoss and Krauss² and that of Shedlovsky³ were applied for the evaluation of the equivalent conductance at zero concentration (Λ°) and the dissociation constant (K). For this the viscosity of the solvent was measured by the method reported by Das et. al.⁴ The dielectric constant was measured from the data of Akerlof and Short⁵ and the methods of extrapolation of Λ° and K were similar to that described by Das et. al.

In table I, the equivalent conductances of KCl at various concentrations and at different solvent compositions have been tabulated. The values of Λ° and K determined by the above two methods are recorded in table II. These values are in good agreement.

The distance of the closest approach of the two ions of the electrolyte has been calculated by both Bjerrum's and Stoke's methods,⁵ and are tabulated in table II. The distance of the ion pairs calculated by both the methods are fairly in good agreement.

TABLE I

Concn. in equiv./litre	10% Dioxane	20% Dioxane ΛOhm^{-1}	30% Dioxane
0.01	141.08	121.21	101.05
0.009	142.10	121.42	101.50
0.008	142.80	122.14	102.23
0.007	145.20	124.83	104.93
0.006	145.94	125.13	105.09
0.005	146.21	126.40	106.83
9.004	148.97	127.12	108.30
0.002	150.80	129.08	109.14
0.002	153.24	131.20	110.30

1. Das et. al., *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 410.
2. Fuoss and Krauss, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 476.
3. Shedlovsky, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1938, **225**.
4. Das et. al., *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 58.
5. Akerlof and Short, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1241.

The Walden product ($\Lambda^\circ \bar{\eta}_0$) have been recorded in table II. It is evident from the data that the factor ($\Lambda^\circ \eta_c$) is more or less constant which indicates that there is minimum solvation effect. The same conclusion can also be drawn from the values of the ionic diameter as it does not change appreciably with the change in dioxane content.

TABLE II

Solvent composition.	Equivalent conductance at zero concentration (Λ°) by		Dissociation Constant $K \times 10^2$ by		Radii of the ion ($a\Lambda^\circ$) pairs by Stoke's $\Lambda^\circ\%$		
	Fouss and Krauss method	Shedlovosky's method	Fouss and Krauss method	Shedlovosky's method	Bjerrum's method	Stoke's method	$\Lambda^\circ\%$
10	165.29	165.29	5.20	5.62	2.20	2.458	1.325
20	139.86	139.86	3.92	4.10	2.26	2.396	1.360
30	116.96	116.96	3.65	3.80	2.36	2.474	1.325

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